

THE MECHANISM OF STATE SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES IN THE FIELD OF SERVICES

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Annotation.

Innovative activity, as a result of qualitative changes in the economy of enterprises, aggregates the influence of all factors and changes depending on the level of participation of consumers in the innovative process. In this regard, it is necessary to form innovative process management systems, to determine the organizational structure and tasks of its units. The system of innovative processes is considered as innovations, innovative potential of the enterprise (region) and innovative infrastructure.

Key words.

Innovation, innovative activity, economy, innovative process

In the process of innovative development of business entities in Uzbekistan, it is important to study in depth the factors affecting the innovative development of enterprises in the field of service, entrepreneurship and service functions, and as a result, to develop scientifically based proposals. The factors mentioned are divided into economic, technological, socio-cultural, demographic and institutional factors, depending on the scope of their influence. Among the listed factors, economic factors make up a particularly large share depending on the scope of their influence. In particular, the scale of markets, the distribution of income of the population, the level of effective demand should be noted.

However, it should not be forgotten that the innovative development of enterprises in the service sector directly depends on the level of entrepreneurial activity, which is not limited to opening one's own business, but also to the presence of innovative elements should be considered, which, in turn, allows us to refer to business entities from the point of view of separation with two main elements:

- innovative activity as a business function;
- actions of the entrepreneur as a performer of this function.

In this regard, it can be concluded that creative business activity in the field of services is carried out in the conditions of risk and uncertainty and it is appropriate to define it as an innovative economic activity aimed not only at profiting, but also at fully and qualitatively satisfying consumer demand. It should be noted that despite the fact that many measures for the development of small business are being implemented, the legal basis for the development of innovative entrepreneurship in [our] the republic of Uzbekistan has not been fully developed. There is a great need for state regulation, especially in the service sector.

It should be noted that favorable conditions have been created by the leadership of the republic of Uzbekistan for the protection of the rights of small businesses and private entrepreneurs.

Most importantly, many laws and regulatory documents have been adopted on the creation of a legal framework, in particular, on the protection of the rights of small businesses and private entrepreneurs and on financial support. However, all measures to create support, business incubators, innovative technology parks, and guarantee funds are mainly aimed at developing the production sector and increasing its share in small businesses.

Taking into account the range of people affected by the decisions made in the development of the service sector, it is appropriate to use innovative management aimed at eliminating factors that negatively affect the activities of enterprises in the service sector.

At the same time, the specificity of creative service industries in a certain area determines the direction of the service industry development strategy and reflects the influence of various factors and conditions on the search for new forms and methods of managing enterprises in this area. . (bring new forms and factors of management)

Innovative activity as a result of qualitative changes in the economy of enterprises, combines the influence of all factors and changes depending on the level of participation of consumers in the innovative process.

In this regard, it will be necessary to form innovative process management systems, to determine the organizational structure and tasks of its units. The system of creative processes is considered as innovations, innovative potential of the enterprise (region) and innovative infrastructure.

The last component creates specific financial, organizational, production and social conditions for the implementation of innovations through information support, material, technical and organizational services, which directly affects the formation of innovative potential of enterprises.

Thus, by summarizing identified socio-economic, organizational and legal problems of innovative development of enterprises in the field of service, the following conclusions can be reached.

Table 1.1

In the 2021 rating, "weak" indicators are indicators that are lagging behind and have no data

t/r	No	Indicators	Ball	Place
1. Management institutions				
1.	1.2.1	Normative quality	17,5	126
2. Human capital and research				
2.	2.1.2	State expenditure on education per pupil, secondary education	m/y	m/y
3.	2.1.4	Assessment in reading, mathematics and natural sciences,	m/y	m/y
4.	2.2.3	The number of foreign citizens studying in local HEIs	0,2	105
5.	2.3.3	World scientific research and experimental construction companies, average costs	0	41
6.	2.3.4	Top 3 average grades of universities according to QS rating	0	74
4. Development of the market				
7.	4.1.3	Gross credit portfolio of microfinance organizations	0	80
8.	4.2.2	Market capitalization	m/y	m/y
9.	4.2.3	Venture investors	m/y	m/y
10.	4.2.4	Recipients of venture capital	m/y	m/y
5. Development of business			m/y	m/y
11.	5.1.1	Employment in scientific sectors, %	m/y	m/y
12.	5.1.5	Women working with degrees	m/y	m/y
13.	5.2.1	Scientific cooperation between universities and industry	m/y	m/y
14.	5.2.2	Status of cluster development	m/y	m/y
15.	5.2.3	General Expenditure on Foreign Funded Research and development (GERD)	0	97
6. Knowledge and technologies				
16.	6.1.2	International applications for international cooperation in the of patent cooperation	0	98
17.	6.1.4	Published scientific and technical articles	2,1	125
18.	6.2.3	Costs of computer software	m/y	m/y
7. Creative results			m/y	m/y
19.	7.1.2	Share of brands in GDP among 5000 leading global brands	m/y	m/y
20.	7.1.4	Creation of ICT and organizational model	m/y	m/y
21.	7.2.3	Entertainment and media market	m/y	m/y

22.	7.3.1	Generic Top Level Domains (gTLDs)	0	131
23.	7.3.4	Creating mobile applications	0	99

Source: The Global Innovation Index 2021 data.

- entrepreneurship in the field of service, as the most promising form of activity in market conditions, is designed to solve the complex problems of filling new markets with competitive services of various industries, stimulate competition and encourage creativity;

- the development of small enterprises in the service sector, in particular, needs state support and is regulated by regulatory legal documents;

- tasks of innovative development of enterprises in the service sector should be in accordance with republican and regional innovative economic development programs, which can be implemented on the basis of improving management within the enterprise by applying new forms and methods that meet existing requirements;

- the participation of local management structures in creating favorable conditions for innovation of service enterprises is necessary.

In our opinion, the increase in the volume of sales of services is accompanied by the demand for innovative (creative) work, the emergence of competitive enterprises, which requires the direction of management influence on the search for new forms and methods of activation and stimulation of innovation in enterprises. , along with the application of marketing methods, extends the service life (maturity stage), which is characterized by relative stability and effective use of strategic advantages. From this point of view, it is possible to distinguish the necessary elements of the management system aimed at their innovative development in enterprises in the service sector: strategic management subsystem included in the process of enterprise management; process management subsystem created for the network of enterprise processes; motivational subsystem (integrated into processes) aimed at improving the performance of processes.

Enterprise innovation management provides such a line of action that allows to overcome technological and market conditions in the field of strategy, financing and organization while achieving long-term effective development. Therefore, the innovative policy of the enterprise in the short-term perspective is, on the one hand, the basis of survival in the market, and on the other hand, it is a factor that actively affects the market balance and inter-industry structure.

An enterprise focused on innovative activity depends on the institutional environment in which it operates, as well as on the internal and social environment,

which includes social innovations, which are the most important intellectual factor of innovative development.

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